

Blouch Validation Results

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Simulated Regimes	4
3	Direct Effect Models	5
3.0.1	$hl = 0.1$	5
3.0.2	$hl = 0.25$	6
3.0.3	$hl = 0.75$	7
4	Adaptation Models	8
4.0.1	$hl = 0.1$	8
4.0.2	$hl = 0.25$	9
4.0.3	$hl = 0.75$	10
5	Direct Effect Adaptation Models	11
5.0.1	$hl = 0.1$	11
5.0.2	$hl = 0.25$	12
5.0.3	$hl = 0.75$	13
6	Multi-Optima models	14
6.1	Multi-Optima Model	14
6.1.1	$hl = 0.1$	14
6.1.2	$hl = 0.25$	15
6.1.3	$hl = 0.75$	16
6.2	Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts	17
6.2.1	$hl = 0.1$	17
6.2.2	$hl = 0.25$	18
6.2.3	$hl = 0.75$	19
6.3	Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	20
6.3.1	$hl = 0.1$	20
6.3.2	$hl = 0.25$	21
6.3.3	$hl = 0.75$	22
7	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Models	23
7.1	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model	23
7.1.1	$hl = 0.1$	23
7.1.2	$hl = 0.25$	24
7.1.3	$hl = 0.75$	25
7.2	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts	26
7.2.1	$hl = 0.1$	26
7.2.2	$hl = 0.25$	27
7.2.3	$hl = 0.75$	28
7.3	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	29
7.3.1	$hl = 0.1$	29
7.3.2	$hl = 0.25$	30
7.3.3	$hl = 0.75$	31
7.4	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects	32
7.4.1	$hl = 0.1$	32

7.4.2	$hl = 0.25$	33
7.4.3	$hl = 0.75$	34
7.5	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects	35
7.5.1	$hl = 0.1$	35
7.5.2	$hl = 0.25$	36
7.5.3	$hl = 0.75$	37
7.6	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered	38
7.6.1	$hl = 0.1$	38
7.6.2	$hl = 0.25$	39
7.6.3	$hl = 0.75$	40
8	Multi-Optima Adaptation Models	41
8.1	Multi-Optima Adaptation Model	41
8.1.1	$hl = 0.1$	41
8.1.2	$hl = 0.25$	42
8.1.3	$hl = 0.75$	43
8.2	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts	44
8.2.1	$hl = 0.1$	44
8.2.2	$hl = 0.25$	45
8.2.3	$hl = 0.75$	46
8.3	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	47
8.3.1	$hl = 0.1$	47
8.3.2	$hl = 0.25$	48
8.3.3	$hl = 0.75$	49
8.4	Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects	50
8.4.1	$hl = 0.1$	50
8.4.2	$hl = 0.25$	51
8.4.3	$hl = 0.75$	52
8.5	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects	53
8.5.1	$hl = 0.1$	53
8.5.2	$hl = 0.25$	54
8.5.3	$hl = 0.75$	55
8.6	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered	56
8.6.1	$hl = 0.1$	56
8.6.2	$hl = 0.25$	57
8.6.3	$hl = 0.75$	58
9	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Models	59
9.1	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model	59
9.1.1	$hl = 0.1$	59
9.1.2	$hl = 0.25$	60
9.1.3	$hl = 0.75$	61
9.2	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts	62
9.2.1	$hl = 0.1$	62
9.2.2	$hl = 0.25$	63
9.2.3	$hl = 0.75$	64
9.3	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	65
9.3.1	$hl = 0.1$	65
9.3.2	$hl = 0.25$	66
9.3.3	$hl = 0.75$	67
9.4	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects	68
9.4.1	$hl = 0.1$	68
9.4.2	$hl = 0.25$	69
9.4.3	$hl = 0.75$	70
9.5	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects .	71
9.5.1	$hl = 0.1$	71
9.5.2	$hl = 0.25$	72
9.5.3	$hl = 0.75$	73

9.6	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered	74
9.6.1	$hl = 0.1$	74
9.6.2	$hl = 0.25$	75
9.6.3	$hl = 0.75$	76

1 Introduction

I evaluated the model’s performance on data I simulated using the Model Validation Code SBR2.R script available in the Validation Code folder in the blouch-project project github.com. All data was simulated on a randomly sampled set of 50 tip species from the 10KTrees primate phylogeny (Arnold et al. 2010). This data were then analyzed using the requisite *Blouch* model, and parameter values were compared to the true parameter values.

For each model I tested data simulated with short, medium, and long half lives. Each model accounted for measurement error. Measurement error was added to the X and Y variables by simulating from a random normal distribution with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 0.01$. All runs were using two chains were 2000 iterations per chain.

Results show that all models are generally able to recover the true parameter values, though at the longest half life (0.75) posterior half-lives are biased downwards - this is because one prior was used for all simulations. Given an empirical analysis, wider priors on the half-life might be explored first, then focusing on the peak to produce more precise estimates.

Note that for the multilevel models, results may include divergent transitions for the centered versions, which can lead to unexplored regions of the posterior distribution. As discussed in Grabowski (in revision), in such cases the non-centered version of the model may remedy these issues.

Note that the figures are labeled V_y to denote the stationary variance, which is labeled v in the main text and the figure legends.

2 Simulated Regimes

Figure 1: Simulated regimes for Multi-Optima Models with two regimes.

3 Direct Effect Models

3.0.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 2: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior prediction, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1; v = 20, \theta = 2, \beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75); v \sim \text{exponential}(5); \theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2); \beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

3.0.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 3: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior prediction, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

3.0.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 4: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior prediction, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

4 Adaptation Models

4.0.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 5: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior prediction, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

4.0.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 6: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior prediction, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

4.0.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 7: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior prediction, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

5 Direct Effect Adaptation Models

5.0.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 8: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

5.0.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 9: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

5.0.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 10: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

6 Multi-Optima models

6.1 Multi-Optima Model

6.1.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 11: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.1.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 12: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.1.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 13: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.2 Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts

6.2.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 14: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.2.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 15: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.2.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 16: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.3 Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

6.3.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 17: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.3.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 18: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

6.3.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 19: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A, B, D) are true values of the parameter.

7 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Models

7.1 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model

7.1.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 20: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.1.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 21: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.1.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 22: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.2 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts

7.2.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 23: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.2.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 24: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.2.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 25: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.3 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

7.3.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 26: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.3.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 27: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.3.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 28: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.4 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects

7.4.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 29: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.4.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 30: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.4.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 31: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.5 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects

7.5.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 32: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.5.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 33: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.5.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 34: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.6 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered

7.6.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 35: Pri or vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.6.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 36: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

7.6.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 37: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8 Multi-Optima Adaptation Models

8.1 Multi-Optima Adaptation Model

8.1.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 38: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1; v = 20, \theta = 2, \beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75); v \sim \text{exponential}(5); \theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.1.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 39: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.1.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 40: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.2 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts

8.2.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 41: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.2.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 42: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.2.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 43: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.3 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

8.3.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 44: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.3.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 45: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.3.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 46: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.4 Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

8.4.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 47: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.4.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 48: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.4.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 49: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A, B, D) are true values of the parameter.

8.5 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

8.5.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 50: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.5.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 51: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.5.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 52: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$ Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.6 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered

8.6.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 53: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.6.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 54: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D) are true values of the parameter.

8.6.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 55: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with species values in black and priors in light grey. Dotted lines overlaying estimated optima are true values of the parameter. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$. Dotted lines in A, B, D) are true values of the parameter.

9 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Models

9.1 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model

9.1.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 56: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.1.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 57: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.1.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 58: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.2 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts

9.2.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 59: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.2.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 60: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.2.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 61: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.3 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

9.3.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 62: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.3.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 63: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.3.3 $hl = 0.75$

9.4 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

9.4.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 65: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.4.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 66: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.4.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 67: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.5 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

9.5.1 $hl = 0.1$

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptive Model – Varying Effects, $hl=0.1$

Figure 68: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.5.2 $hl = 0.25$

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptive Model – Varying Effects, $hl=0.25$

Figure 69: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.5.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 70: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.6 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered

9.6.1 $hl = 0.1$

Figure 71: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.6.2 $hl = 0.25$

Figure 72: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.25$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

9.6.3 $hl = 0.75$

Figure 73: Prior vs. posterior for A) Half-life (hl); B) v ; C) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA with priors (grey lines) and posterior (light red line); and D,E) Posterior prediction means (black line) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for posterior predictions, with priors in light grey. Species values are shown in the dark circles, with dotted line showing true parameter values of intercept and slope. For this simulation parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.75$; $v = 20$, $\theta = 2$, $\beta = 0.25$. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75)$; $v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$; $\theta \sim \text{normal}(2, 0.2)$; $\beta \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.25)$. Dotted lines in A,B,D,E) are true values of the parameter.

Blouch Model Checking Results

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Simulated Regimes	3
3	Basic Models	4
3.0.1	Direct effect Model	4
3.0.2	Adaptation Model	4
3.0.3	Direct Effect Adaptation Model	4
4	Multi-Optima Models	5
4.0.1	Multi-Optima Model	5
4.0.2	Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts	5
4.0.3	Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	5
4.0.4	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model	5
4.0.5	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts	6
4.0.6	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	6
4.0.7	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects	6
4.0.8	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects	7
4.0.9	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered	7
4.0.10	Multi-Optima Adaptation Model	7
4.0.11	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts	8
4.0.12	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	8
4.0.13	Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects	8
4.0.14	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects	9
4.0.15	Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered	9
4.0.16	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model	9
4.0.17	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts	10
4.0.18	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered	10
4.0.19	Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects	10
4.0.20	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects	11
4.0.21	Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered	11
5	References	11

1 Introduction

Prior predictive checks generate predictions from the model using only the prior distribution(s) in order to assess whether the priors are appropriate – they are equivalent to running the model without data (Gabry et al. 2019). Posterior predictive checks generate data

according to the posterior predictive distribution and compare it to the observed data to assess the fit of the model (Gabry et al. 2019). *Blouch* includes Stan functions to run prior and posterior predictive checks for each of the included models, and their use is shown the simulation and empirical examples in the main manuscript and on the vignettes on the *Blouch* github.com site. Below are the results for all models included in the release version of *Blouch*.

I evaluated the model's fit on data I simulated using the Model Checking Code SBR2.R script available in the Model Checking folder in the blouch-project project on GitHub.com. All data was simulated on a randomly sampled set of 50 tip species from the 10KTrees primate phylogeny (Arnold et al. 2010). This data were then analyzed using the requisite *Blouch* model.

All simulations were run with the true parameter values were set to: $hl = 0.1; v = 20$ and other parameter values following those used in the Validation Results. Priors were set to: $hl \sim \text{lognormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75); v \sim \text{exponential}(5)$ with other values following those used in the Validation Results.

Each model accounted for measurement error. Measurement error was added to the X and Y variables by simulating from a random normal distribution with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 0.01$. All runs were using two chains were 2000 iterations per chain.

For each model the Prior and Posterior Check results shows the density estimates of the observed species data (in blue) versus the simulated data (in pale red) drawn from the posterior distribution.

Results show that all models are well fit, with simulated data looking similar to the observed data.

2 Simulated Regimes

Figure 1: Simulated regimes for Multi-Optima Models

3 Basic Models

3.0.1 Direct effect Model

Figure 2: Prior Predictive Check

Figure 3: Posterior Predictive Check

3.0.2 Adaptation Model

3.0.3 Direct Effect Adaptation Model

4 Multi-Optima Models

4.0.1 Multi-Optima Model

4.0.2 Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts

4.0.3 Multilevel Multi-Optima Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

4.0.4 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model

Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Prior PC

Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Posterior PC

4.0.5 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Intercepts – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Intercepts – Posterior PC

4.0.6 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Intercepts – Non-centered – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Intercepts – Non-centered – Posterior PC

4.0.7 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects

Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Effects – Prior PC

Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Effects – Posterior PC

4.0.8 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Effects – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Effects – Posterior PC

4.0.9 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Effects – Non-centered – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model – Varying Effects – Non-centered Posterior PC

4.0.10 Multi-Optima Adaptation Model

Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Prior PC

Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Posterior PC

4.0.11 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Posterior PC

4.0.12 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Non-centered – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Non-centered – Posterior PC

4.0.13 Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Effects – Prior PC

Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Effects – Posterior PC

4.0.14 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Effects – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Effects – Posterior PC

4.0.15 Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Effects – Non-centered – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptation Model – Varying Effects – Non-centered – Posterior PC

4.0.16 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model

Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptation Model – Prior PC

Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptation Model – Posterior PC

4.0.17 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Posterior PC

4.0.18 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Intercepts - Non-centered

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Non-centered – Prior PC

Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect + Adaptation Model – Varying Intercepts – Non-centered – Posterior PC

4.0.19 Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

4.0.20 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects

4.0.21 Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Adaptation Model - Varying Effects - Non-centered

5 References

Arnold, C., L. J. Matthews, and C. L. Nunn. 2010. The 10kTrees Website: A New Online Resource for Primate Phylogeny. *Evolutionary Anthropology* 19:114-118.

Gabry J., Simpson D., Vehtari A., Betancourt M., Gelman A. 2019. Visualization in Bayesian workflow. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series A (Statistics in Society)*. 182:389–402.